

**A STUDY ON CONSUMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS
PATANJALI WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE CITY**
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Abstract:

India and ayurved are very closely related words. Consumers look for the healthy products along with the quality because in the modern India there is a great awareness about the healthy life style. Yoga, Ayurveda, Natural therapies are the utmost considered concepts than any other medicines. There is more consideration for the avoidance of unwanted stuffs than the cure of the diseases. Hence this gives lot of weightage to the Yoga Guru Baba Ramdev and his naturally positioned Patanjali products. This paper throws light on the consumer's perception and satisfaction towards the Patanjali brand. Also this paper will tell about the problems faced by consumers with the use of Patanjali products. The conclusion is that though the company is having variety of products the customers are not aware of the products and that can be optimized by providing free samples through various sources. The company can increase the flavors of the product so that the profit can be optimized in future period of time.

Key Words: Patanjali, FMCG, Ayurved, Brand, India & Consumer Perception

Introduction:

Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector is the 4th largest sector in the Indian economy with Household and Personal Care accounting for 50 per cent of FMCG sales in India. Growing awareness, easier access and changing lifestyles have been the key growth drivers for the sector. The urban segment (accounts for a revenue share of around 55 per cent) is the largest contributor to the overall revenue generated by the FMCG sector in India. However, in the last few years, the FMCG market has grown at a faster pace in rural India compared with urban India. The Retail market in India is estimated to reach US\$ 1.1 trillion by 2020 from US\$ 840 billion in 2017, with modern trade expected to grow at 20 per cent - 25 per cent per annum, which is likely to boost revenues of FMCG companies. The top FMCG companies in India are Patanjali, Hindustan Unilever, Procter & Gamble, Godrej, Dabur, Amul, Britannia, Colgate-Palmolive, Coca Cola, PepsiCo, ITC and many more. While most of them are foreign organizations, Patanjali became successful beating all these companies. The revenue of Patanjali was about Rs.5000 crores in the fiscal year 2015-2016, while it increased to Rs.10,561 crores in the year 2016-2017.

Patanjali Ayurved Limited is an Indian FMCG company. Manufacturing units and headquarters are located in the industrial area of Haridwar while the registered office is located at Delhi. The company manufactures mineral and herbal products. It also has manufacturing units in Nepal under the trademark Nepal Gramudhyog and imports majority of herbs in India from Himalayas of Nepal. According to CLSA and HSBC, Patanjali is the fastest growing FMCG company in India. It is valued at ₹30 billion (US\$450 million) and some predict revenues of ₹5,000 crore (US\$740 million) for the fiscal 2015-2016. Ramdev baba has stated in his interview with CNN-News18 that profit from Patanjali Products goes to charity.

Problem of the Study:

The main problem of the study is

- ✓ Customers are satisfied towards the quality and delivery of products?
- ✓ Customer perception towards brand image?

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study about the demographic profile of the respondents.
- ✓ To analyse the perception of customers towards Patanjali products.
- ✓ To analyse the level of awareness of customers towards various products available in the market.
- ✓ To know about the level of satisfaction of customers towards Patanjali products.

Scope of the Study:

The main scope of the study is that it will be helpful for the company to know about the performance of themselves which will be useful for them in future period of time. It will help the company to know about the

satisfaction of customers towards the products of the company helping in changing the quality based on customer preference.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

A research design is the specification of methods and procedure for acquiring the information needed. Research design classified under three broad categories – explanatory, casual and descriptive. But the researcher was concerned mainly with descriptive research design. The study was conducted in order to find out the customer satisfaction towards Patanjali products.

Sampling Techniques:

- ✓ Sampling Plan: One of the main elements in the research design is sampling plan which is further divided into sampling unit, sampling size, sampling type.
- ✓ Sampling Unit: Sampling unit can be defined as the basic unit containing the customer satisfaction towards Patanjali products.
- ✓ Sampling Size: In this research, the sample size amount to two hundred and fifty, which are surveyed from customers who purchase Patanjali.
- ✓ Sampling Type: Convenience sampling I adapted in this research. It is a non-probability sampling and it refers to selecting a sample based on convenience. And also, the statistical tool are applied viz. (a) chi-square test (b) Percentage analysis and ranking method.

Data Collection:

The primary data the respondents which or collected with a questionnaire schedule was used with customers of the company.

Secondary data were collected from the company profile, manuals, journals, magazines and newspapers etc.

Tertiary Data: The data were collected from the various literatures which are related to the subject of customers of the company.

Research Tool: Structures self administered questionnaire had been used as a research tool for collecting

Primary Data: The questionnaire from is designed in the multi choice pattern and has the following technique.

Direct Questions: In this type, the respondents were asked to answer directly to their questions.

Indirect Questions: Indirect questions refer to those whose responses are used to indicate or suggest information.

Open Ended Questions: In this type, respondents are likely to choose their answers.

Closed Ended Questions: Respondents are offered to select their options given.

- ✓ Multiple Choice Type (Objective Type)

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The sample size is limited to 250.
- ✓ There is a bias in collecting the data as they say the answers wrongly.
- ✓ The study area is limited to Coimbatore.

Analysis and Interpretation:

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	66	26.4
	Female	184	73.6
	Total	250	100
Age	Below 20 years	16	6.4
	21-30 years	100	40
	31-40 years	66	26.4
	41-50 years	48	19.2
	Above 50 years	20	8
	Total	250	100
Educational Qualification	School level	32	12.8
	Under graduate	128	51.2
	Post graduate	84	33.6
	Professional	6	2.4
	Total	250	100
Marital Status	Married	148	59.2
	Unmarried	102	40.8
	Total	250	100
Occupation	Student	80	32
	Employed	64	25.6
	Business	18	7.2
	Profession	16	6.4

	House wife	72	28.8
	Total	250	100
Monthly Family Income	Up to Rs.25000	18	7.2
	Rs.25000 to Rs.50000	110	44
	Rs.50000 to 75000	104	41.6
	Above Rs.75000	18	7.2
	Total	250	100
Place of Residence	Rural	48	19.2
	Urban	202	80.8
	Total	250	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the gender of the respondents were out of 250 respondents 26.4% are male and 73.6% are female. 6.4% are from the age group of below 20 years, 40% are from the age group of 21-30 years, 26.4% are from the age group of 31-40 years, 19.25 are from the age group of 41-50 years and 8% are from the age group of above 50 years. 6.4% are from the age group of below 20 years, 40% are from the age group of 21-30 years, 26.4% are from the age group of 31-40 years, 19.25 are from the age group of 41-50 years and 8% are from the age group of above 50 years. 59.2% are married and 40.8% are unmarried. 32% are students, 25.6% are employed, 7.2% are doing business, 6.4% are professionals and 28.8% are house wife. 7.2% are earning up to Rs.25000, 44% are earning from Rs.25000 to Rs.50000, 41.6% are earning from Rs.50000 to 75000, 7.2% are earning above Rs.75000. 19.2% are from rural area and 80.8% are from urban area.

Awareness towards Patanjali:

	Frequency	Percent
Highly aware	18	7.2
Aware	138	55.2
Neutral	90	36
Slightly aware	4	1.6
Total	250	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about awareness towards Patanjali were out of 250 respondents 7.2% are highly aware, 55.2% are aware, 36% are neutral and 1.6% are slightly aware. It shows that most of the respondents are aware about Patanjali products.

Awareness towards Products of Patanjali:

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Awareness towards Grocery and Staples	112	44.8
Awareness towards ready Food	34	13.6
Awareness towards beverage	34	13.6
Awareness towards personal care	166	66.4
Awareness towards HealthCare	30	12
Awareness towards House Holds	42	16.8

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the awareness towards Patanjali products were out of 250 respondents 44.8% said that they are aware of grocery and staples, 13.6% said that they are aware of ready food, 13.6% said that they are aware of beverage, 66.4% are aware of products with personal care, 12% are aware of health care products, and 16.8% are aware of house hold products.

Awareness towards Newly Introduced Patanjali Ayrurved Products:

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Awareness towards Noodles	86	34.4
Awareness towards Chocolate	40	16
Awareness towards Basmathi Rice	70	28
Awareness towards Health Drink	24	9.6
Awareness towards Toothpaste	146	58.4
Awareness towards Other products	16	6.4

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the Awareness towards newly introduced Patanjali Ayrurved products were 34.4% are aware about noodles, 16% are aware about Chocolate, 28% are aware about Basmathi rice, 9.6% are aware about health drink, 58.4% are aware about tooth paste and 6.4% are aware about other products.

Level of Satisfaction towards Adulteration Free Products:

	Frequency	Percent
Neutral	44	39.3
Dissatisfied	66	58.9
Highly dissatisfied	2	1.8
Total	112	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about level of satisfaction towards adulteration free products were out of 112 respondents 39.3% are neutral, 58.9% are dissatisfied and 1.8% are highly dissatisfied towards adulteration free products. It shows that most of the respondents are dissatisfied towards adulteration of free products.

Age * Level of satisfaction towards adulteration free products

H₀: There is no significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards adulteration free products

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.684 ^a	8	0.017

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards adulteration free products were the level of significance is at 0.017 which is lesser than 0.05. It shows that there is a significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards adulteration free products.

Age * Level of satisfaction towards chemical free

H₀: There is no significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards chemical free

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.244 ^a	6	0

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards chemical free were the level of significance is at 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05. It shows that there is a significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards chemical free.

Rank Correlation for Factor Influencing to Buy the Product:

S.No	Ranking on Company and Scheme	X	Y	R1	R2	D	D ²
1	Price	40	70	3.5	2	1.5	2.25
2	Quality of the product	40	72	3.5	1	2.5	6.25
3	Quantity of the product	2	10	7	6	1	1
4	Variety of the product	6	0	5	10	-5	25
5	Packaging	0	2	10	9	1	1
6	Availability	44	30	2	4	-2	4
7	Promotion	1	6	9	7	2	4
8	Preservation	2	4	7	8	-1	1
9	Proximity	116	36	1	3	-2	4
10	Herbal Products	2	26	7	5	2	4
							52.5
N	10					1-R	0.32
						R	0.68

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the correlation between ranks given for factor influencing to buy the product were the correlation is at 0.68 which is moderately correlated. It shows that the factor Proximity is given highest priority.

Findings:

- ✓ Most of the respondents are female in our survey.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are from the age group of 21-30 years.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are from the age group of 21-30 years.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are married in our survey.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are students in our survey.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are earning from Rs.25000 to Rs.50000.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are from urban area.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents have 2 to 4 members in their family.
- ✓ Most of the respondents have up to 2 members in their family.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are aware about Patanjali products.

- ✓ Most of the respondents are using Patanjali ayurved product for less than 6 months.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the product is available with the market.
- ✓ Most of the respondents purchase Patanjali Ayurvedic products through dealers and exclusive store.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are dissatisfied towards adulteration of free products.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are dissatisfied towards consistency.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are dissatisfied towards natural preservation.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are neutral towards reasonable price.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are neutral towards nutritious.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards fast recovery.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards no side effects.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards non toxic.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards natural ingredients.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards chemical free.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards multiple uses.
- ✓ There is a significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction towards safe to use.
- ✓ The factor Proximity is given highest priority based on rank correlation.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The company can concentrate more reducing adulteration by having a separate quality checking and quality assistance for the company so that the quality of the product can be increased and the level of satisfaction can be increased in future period.
- ✓ To increase the sales the availability of consistency of the products can increased in future period of time.
- ✓ The advertisement campaigns can be conducted by female customers as the respondents are female in our survey which will increase the sales and profit of the company.
- ✓ Refrigeration can be used to preserve the products for a short period of time which can increase the quality of the product.
- ✓ The company can concentrate more on corporate governance towards price of the product as the customers are not aware of price of product and for this more pamphlets can be placed all over the country projecting price of the product which leads to increase in sales and brand vale of the product.
- ✓ Though the company is having variety of products the customers are not aware of the products and that can be optimized by providing free samples through various sources.
- ✓ The company can increase the flavors of the product so that the profit can be optimized in future period of time.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that though the company is having variety of products the customers are not aware of the products and that can be optimized by providing free samples through various sources. The company can increase the flavors of the product so that the profit can be optimized in future period of time.

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